

Climateurope2

Final assessment of organised activities and recommendations for future events

Deliverable 6.4

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About Climateurope2

Timely delivery and effective use of climate information is fundamental for a green recovery and a resilient, climate neutral Europe, in response to climate change and variability. Climate services address this through the provision of climate information for use in decision-making to manage risks and realise opportunities.

The market and needs for climate information have seen impressive progress in recent years and is expected to grow in the foreseeable future. However, the communities involved in the development and provision of climate services are often unaware of each other and lack interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary knowledge. In addition, quality assurance, relevant standards, and other forms of assurance (such as guidelines, and good practices) for climate services are lagging behind. These are needed to ensure the saliency, credibility, legitimacy, and authoritativeness of climate services, and build two-way trust between supply and demand.

Climateurope2 aims to develop future equitable and quality-assured climate services to all sectors of society by:

- Developing standardisation procedures for climate services
- Supporting an equitable European climate services community
- Enhancing the uptake of quality-assured climate services to support adaptation and mitigation to climate change and variability

The project will identify the support and standardisation needs of climate services, including criteria for certification and labelling, as well as the user-driven criteria needed to support climate action. This information will be used to propose a taxonomy of climate services, suggest community-based good practices and guidelines, and propose standards where possible. A large variety of activities to support the communities involved in European climate services will also be organised.

Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the final report on the stakeholder engagement activities implemented within Work Package 6 (WP6) of the Climateurope2 project. Building upon the previous deliverables, it consolidates the experience gathered throughout the project and reflects on the effectiveness, impact, and legacy of the engagement strategy developed to support the European climate services community.

WP6 aims to foster open exchange of knowledge, expertise, and collaboration among organisations and individuals involved in the development, provision, and use of climate services. A key objective was to expand and strengthen the Climateurope2 Network by engaging a diverse range of stakeholders across sectors, regions, and governance levels, while building on the foundations established by the original Climateurope project. Particular attention was given to improving inclusiveness, strengthening participation from underrepresented regions such as South-East Europe, and supporting dialogue across the climate services value chain.

The Climateurope2 Network has grown significantly during the project and currently includes more than 600 registered members from all continents. The network demonstrates a balanced representation across academia, public institutions, private-sector actors, and NGOs, while also maintaining a positive gender balance. Beyond formally registered members, approximately 1,400 contacts have engaged with the project through events and communication activities.

The WP6 engagement strategy was structured around two complementary dimensions: communication channels and interactive events. Communication activities relied on the Climateurope2 website, Platform, and social media channels, which collectively supported dissemination, visibility, and continuous interaction with stakeholders. The [Climateurope2 Platform](#), publicly launched in late 2025, has evolved into a significant knowledge-sharing and exploitation tool, offering access to guidelines, training modules, glossaries, key messages, and other project outputs.

A broad portfolio of engagement events was implemented throughout the project, including webinars, Webstivals, Festivals, regional Roadshows, sectoral workshops, and sessions at major international conferences. These activities successfully created spaces for dialogue, networking, co-production, and exchange between researchers, policymakers, climate service providers, businesses, and civil society actors. In particular, the in-person Festivals in Venice and Belgrade, as well as the Roadshow in South-East Europe, proved highly effective in fostering participation, strengthening regional engagement, and broadening the visibility of climate services beyond technical and academic audiences. The integration of art+science approaches further contributed to making climate services more accessible, socially relevant, and publicly engaging.

Finally, the deliverable identifies key lessons learned and formulates recommendations for future initiatives. Findings suggest that engagement activities are most effective when they combine interactive formats, targeted stakeholder outreach, local partnerships, and opportunities for co-creation. In-person and locally grounded events were particularly successful in building trust and long-term connections, while online activities benefited from shorter, participatory, and discussion-oriented formats. Future projects should further strengthen post-event follow-up mechanisms, expand multilingual and locally adapted communication, and continue integrating artistic and societal dimensions into climate service engagement. These recommendations contribute to the long-term legacy of Climateurope2 and support the continued development of an open, inclusive, and collaborative European climate services community.

Keywords

Climate services community, Climateurope2 Network, stakeholder engagement, events, platform, social media, diversity, equity and inclusiveness

1 Aim of the deliverable

This deliverable presents the final report on the virtual and face-to-face engagement activities carried out with the Climateurope2 Network within the framework of Work Package 6 (WP6). It represents the last and final report in a series of four deliverables documenting the development, implementation, and monitoring of the Climateurope2 community engagement strategy. Building on the previous reports ([D6.1](#), [D6.2](#), and [D6.3](#)), this document consolidates the activities implemented throughout the project and provides a reflective assessment of their outcomes. In particular, it focuses on the lessons learned from the engagement activities and formulates recommendations for future initiatives targeting the climate services community, while also reflecting on the legacy of Climateurope2.

WP6 aims to promote open exchange of knowledge, expertise, and data across the climate services community, defined as the network of organisations and individuals involved in the development, provision, and use of climate services. A key objective of the work package has been to establish, expand, and actively engage a diverse and inclusive European network of stakeholders, building upon the foundations laid by the first Climateurope project (2016–2021). In doing so, WP6 has sought to strengthen collaboration across sectors, improve representation of underrepresented groups and regions, and facilitate knowledge exchange across the climate services value chain.

The engagement strategy developed in WP6 relies on two complementary pillars: communication channels and interactive events. Communication channels, including the [Climateurope2 project website](#), the [Climateurope2 online platform](#), and social media, serve as key tools for disseminating information and maintaining continuous interaction with the network. In parallel, a range of engagement events have been organised to foster dialogue, share experiences, and strengthen connections within the community. These include webinars, Webstivals and Festivals, a regional Roadshow in South-East Europe, workshops targeting private sector and standardisation stakeholders, and dedicated sessions at major conferences and events.

In addition to strengthening the Climateurope2 Network itself, WP6 has supported clustering and collaboration with sister projects, institutional stakeholders, and other initiatives, thereby contributing to the broader ecosystem of climate services in Europe. The work package has also played an important role in connecting the climate services community with the activities of other project work packages, ensuring that community perspectives inform key project outputs, particularly those related to the development of standards and quality frameworks for climate services.

This deliverable reports on the engagement activities carried out since the submission of the previous deliverable (May 2025) and provides an overview of the evolution of the Climateurope2 Network. However, rather than focusing solely on the technical documentation of activity, which is also addressed through the project's communication and dissemination work, this report places particular emphasis on evaluating the effectiveness and impact of engagement efforts. Each section therefore reflects on the experience gained through the different types of activities implemented during the project.

The final section of the deliverable synthesises these reflections to identify key lessons learned, highlighting successful practices as well as challenges encountered in engaging a diverse climate services community. Based on this analysis, the report provides recommendations for the design and implementation of engagement activities in future projects and initiatives, contributing to the long-term legacy of Climateurope2 and supporting the continued development of an open, inclusive, and collaborative European climate services community.

2 Current status of the Climateurope2 Network

The Climateurope2 Network is continuously growing, reaching more than 600 (622 on 29/05/2026) registered members and bringing together stakeholders from a wide range of sectors and countries. Membership of the Climateurope2 Network is voluntary and is consistently offered whenever the project engages external stakeholders¹. Joining the network enables stakeholders to remain connected with the climate services community and gain direct access to information through the Climateurope2 Platform (see Section 3.2), participate in the discussion on climate services standardisation, and be informed about the activities bringing the network together. To do so, the project coordination by Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC) (through WP7) monitors and maintains all community membership data, including geographical distribution, sectoral representation, and gender distribution. WP6, in turn, uses this data to support the planning, targeting, and implementation of stakeholder engagement activities.

Figure 1. Climateurope2 Network density map showing the worldwide location of network members (the network list is current as of May 2026)

While membership remains most strongly concentrated in Europe, the network includes representatives from every continent. In particular, following a series of South-East Europe-focused

¹ Stakeholders are redirected to the [registration page](#) to join the network and are invited to take a look at the [network flyer](#).

activities (described below), such as roadshows, Festivals, and other engagement events, the region experienced a significant increase in membership. To give an example, after the second iteration of the Roadshows from March 2026, the network saw an increase of 28 people from the region. Figure 1, above, presents the global distribution of Climateurope2 Network members, while Figure 2, below, provides a more detailed overview of membership across European countries.

Figure 2. Network members across European countries

The network has not only expanded significantly but is also reaching a broader range of sectors. Given the scientific nature of the topic, Research and Academia remains the most represented sector, with 208 participants. However, non-academic stakeholders from both the Public and Private sectors are closely represented, with 166 and 167 participants respectively. This is a positive development, as it demonstrates our success in engaging not only the research community but also both users and providers of operational climate services. The remaining members of the network are primarily affiliated with NGOs (67 participants), while a smaller proportion comes from the media sector. The distribution of participants across sectors is illustrated in Figure 3².

² Since the registration process requires stakeholders to voluntarily provide their information, not all registrants have specified their sector or country of origin.

Figure 3. Distribution of Network participants among sectors

With regard to gender balance, the network shows a slight female majority, with women representing 53% of participants and men representing 44%. A small proportion of members belong to gender minorities or prefer not to disclose their gender. A detailed breakdown of the network's gender composition is presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Gender distribution of Network participants

As already mentioned, the network includes only individuals who have voluntarily registered. The online and in-person events organized by Climateurope2 often engage many more participants whose contact details, when explicitly authorized through the consent clause included in the event registration

process, are stored in the GDPR-compliant online database Contacts-App created by BSC and managed by WP7. This broader community consists of around 1400 contacts, and was taken into consideration to better assess the sectoral composition of the Network.

For all contacts in the Contacts-App, sectoral affiliation and areas of interest were researched via sources such as their affiliated organisation, LinkedIn, ResearchGate or Google Scholar. These results were compared with the broader landscape of climate services activity using the dashboard connected to the CE2 Platform. Online searches were performed by creating 'bookmarks' combining the term 'climate services' with 14 different sectors. The 14 sectors were based on the division in sectors by the [Copernicus sectoral services](#). The dashboard aggregates multilingual Web content (English, German, Spanish, French) from news outlets, research portals, NGOs and company sites. For this analysis, the context filter "climate services" was applied over the period 1 April 2024 - 31 March 2026, returning 1,237 documents that mention climate services and at least one European location (extracted via WLT's geotagging service). See Figure 5 for the results.

Figure 5. Climateurope2 visual analytics dashboard with the context filter "climate services" applied for 1 April 2024 – 31 March 2026 (1,237 matching documents). The left sidebar shows counts for each of the 14 Copernicus sectors; the top five are selected for colour-coded comparison

The number of results found per sector were regarded as a proxy for the activity in climate services for each sector. By comparing the percentages of each search, we made an estimate if our present network is representative. In case of significant discrepancies, targeted activities to specific sectors may be needed in the remainder of the project.

The results of the analysis are shown in Figure 6. In an ideal scenario, all bar couples (one blue, one orange) would have a similar length. Sectors with greater levels of activity would be expected to have a correspondingly larger representation within the network, whereas sectors with lower activity levels may naturally account for fewer members. In the analysis, three categories only have a blue bar: “*climate modelling, climate adaptation*”, “*media, communication, participation*”, and “*marine*”. Out of these, the first two categories represent a large fraction of the network, but they are not Copernicus sectors. These categories were assigned only when more specific sectoral classifications were not appropriate. For example, the Met office often addresses climate for a broad range of sectors instead of only one. The same often applies to media and government, where climate and adaptation is addressed in the broad sense and not related to a specific sector.

Figure 6. Network sectoral composition vs activity in climate services for each sector

For the remaining sectors, representation can be considered adequate when the blue bar is at the same level as, or higher than, the orange bar. Where the orange bar is significantly higher, additional efforts may be needed to strengthen engagement and participation from those sectors. This is particularly the case for the following sectors: *Disaster risk & Extreme events*; *Water management*; *Biodiversity*; *Infrastructure & transport (ICT)*; *Mountains*.

3 Channels for engagement

This chapter explains the role of the project website, the interactive platform, and social media in engaging existing and new community members in Climateurope2. These communication channels are managed by WP7, while WP6 utilises them.

3.1 Climateurope2 project website

The Climateurope2 website (<https://climateurope2.eu/>) continued to serve as the central hub for project information throughout the duration of the project. It was regularly updated with news on project activities, events organised by the consortium, and external initiatives of relevance to the climate services community. In this way, the website remained a key channel for disseminating results and maintaining stakeholder engagement.

As the project advanced and new outputs were generated, the website structure was further developed to improve user access to information and encourage engagement with project results. In particular, a **new main menu section entitled “Guidelines & Standards”** was created to host key project outputs. Under this section, two new dedicated pages were launched: [Key Messages](#) and [Joint Statements](#).

The **“Key Messages”** page presents the annual recommendations prepared by WP1 as part of the process of identifying priorities for the standardisation of climate services. These recommendations are intended to support the development of quality-assured, accessible, and user-oriented climate services, while fostering a more equitable and connected community. To facilitate access to this content, the material is made available in two formats: the full synthesis report and a concise summary version.

The **“Joint Statements”** page showcases outputs of sectoral engagement events organised through WP8. These events form part of the project’s wider stakeholder consultation strategy and provide a forum for gathering perspectives from different sectors on the standardisation of climate services. The resulting statements represent consolidated stakeholder input and contribute to the development of trusted, accessible, and high-quality climate services.

Additionally, to improve access to information and in response to the growing number of project events organised, a filtering function was incorporated into the **“Past events”** page, enabling users to more easily identify and browse specific categories of events according to their interests and needs.

The website continued to provide several features aimed at strengthening interaction and connectivity across the community. The CE2 homepage includes a **“Join Our Network”** function, enabling interested stakeholders to register in order to receive updates and participate in project activities. The registration form clearly states that the information provided will be used to maintain contact regarding project news, opportunities, and events. The homepage was also regularly refreshed with project highlights, including events and news from the project.

To date, Climateurope2 has published five biannual **newsletters**. Previously, newsletter subscribers and network members were managed through separate subscription options. However, as expanding the project network became a strategic priority, and both groups were already receiving the newsletter, the standalone newsletter subscription button was removed from the homepage. However, individuals who had previously subscribed only to the newsletter continue to receive newsletter communications, while network members receive broader project-related updates during the year. In addition, participants in project events who provided consent to receive further information about the project results and events have been incorporated into the mailing list. In total, the newsletter is currently distributed to more than 1500 contacts.

The **blog** is the most engagement-oriented section of the website, designed for members of the climate services community, especially for members external to the project, to share short, accessible articles on topics of interest, such as good practices, sector-specific insights, or the role of standardisation. It supports knowledge exchange and aims to position the website as a reference point for climate services discussions, while also increasing the project’s visibility and attracting new visitors.

The website maintained a dedicated section for **upcoming events**, featuring both project-organised activities and other relevant events related to climate services organised by external initiatives or partner organisations.

The website also continued to provide direct communication channels with stakeholders. Through the **online contact form**, visitors may submit questions or comments to the project team. In addition, the team at Barcelona Supercomputing Centre can be contacted directly via the dedicated project email address: infoclimateurope2@bsc.es.

Website performance and user reach are monitored by WP7 through Google Analytics. Between May 2025 and March 2026, a total of 6,343 **visits** were recorded, from 1,848 different users.

The **traffic distribution** shows how users are reaching the website:

- Direct (56.49%) indicates that most users arrive by typing the URL directly, using bookmarks, or through untracked links.
- Organic search (24.39%) shows users finding the site via search engines, reflecting visibility in search results.
- Referral (11.18%) represents users coming from links on other websites, indicating external mentions and dissemination through partners or related platforms.
- Organic social (7.86%) refers to users arriving via unpaid posts on social media, showing a smaller but relevant contribution from social channels.

Looking at **page views** (the total number of times a page was visited), and excluding the Home page, the five most visited pages were:

- [Climateurope2 Festival in Belgrade event page](#)
- [Events main page](#)
- [“Trustworthy climate information for effective physical climate risk assessment” event page](#)
- [Platform page](#)
- [Past events page](#)

The results suggest that events were a key driver of engagement. Users also showed interest in the Platform.

Looking at **landing page sessions** (the pages users entered the website through), and excluding the Home page, the five most common entry pages were:

- [Climateurope2 Festival in Belgrade page](#)
- [“Trustworthy climate information for effective physical climate risk assessment” event page](#)
- [Fifth Climateurope2 Webstival event page](#)
- [“Standardising Climate Services in Europe: a dialogue with national meteorological and hydrological services” event page](#)
- [“Building trust in European climate services: a joint industry statement” page](#)

This metric shows which pages were most effective at attracting users to the website in the first place. The results indicate what pages played an important role in bringing audiences to Climateurope2, highlighting their value as entry points for outreach and communication activities.

What worked well

The website remained highly dynamic throughout the year, with new content regularly published and updated. It continued to serve as a central access point for project activities, outputs, events, and stakeholder resources, supporting the visibility and accessibility of project results across the climate services community.

The improvements introduced during the reporting period, including the new “*Guidelines & Standards*” menu section, highlighted content on the homepage, and the filter function in the Past Events section enhanced the overall structure and functionality of the website. These changes improved the site’s navigability, making it easier for users to locate and access relevant information.

The newly created “*Guidelines & Standards*” section was rapidly populated with project outputs and became an important dissemination resource for partners, who actively promoted the materials through their own communication channels, networks, and events.

Areas for improvement

The “*Other Events*” section would benefit from a more reciprocal approach to collecting external event information. Currently, inputs mainly come from sister projects, while broader community contributions are limited. A more structured exchange with the wider climate services community would help ensure a more continuous and proactive flow of relevant event information.

The project blog has the potential to become a more dynamic and interactive space. So far, contributions have mostly come through targeted invitations rather than spontaneous input. Increasing promotion of the blog and allowing more open contributions could improve engagement and enable more varied personal storytelling on climate services.

Finally, expanding multilingual content would improve accessibility and inclusiveness, especially for audiences in Eastern Europe, which is a relevant target group for the project. This would, however, require additional time and financial resources.

3.2 Climateurope2 Platform

The CE2 Platform (platform.climateurope2.eu) was developed in WP7 and includes four sections:

- 1) *Co-create* to enter documents (guidelines, standards, good practices) with standardised metadata (title, tags, etc.);
- 2) *Explore* to showcase the documents and allow for faceted searching and filtering;
- 3) *Analytics* to provide visualisation services and explore content; and
- 4) *Connect* to host information about members in the network.

For a full description, we refer to the [D7.5](#). The Platform is now fully operational and is an important part of the exploitation strategy of CE2.

The Platform is openly accessible, and it was publicly launched during the Climateurope2 Festival in September 2025 through an in-person workshop. Subsequently, in November 2025, a webinar from the [Stakeholders’ Perspectives series](#)³ was dedicated entirely to presenting the Platform, its functionalities, and potential applications to external audiences. In addition, a promotional video explaining the Platform’s main features was produced and made available on the project website at <https://climateurope2.eu/platform>.

Since the launch of the platform in November until the time of writing (end of May), 11,500 visitors have been recorded, with an average of 5 actions (page visits, downloads, searches and outlinks) per visit, from all over the world (see Figure 6). WP6 has suggested to promote the use of the Platform by the consortium partners. Increased internal use is expected to generate more relevant content while also allowing the consortium to draw on its own experience to further improve the Platform’s accessibility, visibility, and usability. In addition, some of the analytics presented in Section 2 were produced using Platform tools.

³ More information on the Stakeholder’s Perspective webinars series in section 4.1.

Figure 7. Origin of Platform visitors in the period 1-11-2025 to 26-05-2026

The CE2 consortium continues to populate the Platform with outputs generated by the project. Once the Platform is considered sufficiently populated, regularly used by project partners, and therefore easier to understand and navigate for external users, a broader promotional campaign will be launched. The Platform is also expected to be showcased again during the final Webstival planned for late 2026. In terms of exploitation of the platform, the focus will be on the repository and knowledge brokerage aspects, which means a focus on the added value of discovering quality-controlled documents, covering guidelines, recommendations and synthesis reports. This is supported by the development of a new template for the platform content, aiming for a more harmonised collection of documents on the platform.

Significant progress has been made in recent months in expanding the Platform content. Efforts have also been undertaken to systematise and harmonise formats in order to facilitate navigation and improve the overall user experience. In this context, three new sections have been added under “Explore the Library” (

Figure 8):

- **Glossary:** a collection of terms related to climate services that have been defined or endorsed by the project.
- **Training modules:** a set of training materials developed by project work packages to strengthen understanding and uptake of climate services across Europe. The section currently contains eight modules, including a tutorial on how to use the Platform, which can be accessed directly through the main menu under Tutorial.
- **Key Messages:** a dedicated section containing the key messages from the WP1 synthesis report.

These developments strengthen the Platform’s role as a long-term knowledge hub and collaboration space for the climate services community.

Figure 8. Homepage of the Climateurope2 Platform

See all documentation

Our document section is a valuable resource for anyone seeking to stay up-to-date on the latest research and developments in climate services. Here, you can find a wide range of documents, including guidelines, vocabulary, reports, papers, and presentations, all of which are available for download.

<h3>Key messages</h3> <p>The annual Climateurope2 synthesis report.</p> <p>Explore ></p>		
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3.3 Social media

Several social media channels are used in the project to engage with several audiences, including members of the Climateurope2 Network. The goal of the social media activities is mainly to create engagement and acquire new network members through the promotion of the project itself, its outputs, and the activities that are organised.

Climateurope2 developed communities on LinkedIn, YouTube and X (previously Twitter), and at the end of 2024 also launched a [CE2 Bluesky account](#). This new network was supposed to act as an alternative to X. However, the CE2 X account is still active since we have a large community that was inherited from the former Climateurope project. Maintenance of the LinkedIn, X, and Bluesky accounts are part of Task 7.1 (WP7).

While social media is managed and tracked by WP7, it is useful to have an overview of the build-up of followers and engaged users, as it is another indicator for the growth of the Climateurope2 Network. By May 2026, [Climateurope2's X](#) account had 2,340 followers. [Climateurope2's BlueSky account](#), launched at the end of 2024, has grown to 58 followers, while its [LinkedIn page](#) now has 1,977 followers compared to 1269 at May 2025. [Climateurope2 YouTube channel](#) (see Figure 9), with 67 subscribers, 127 videos published, 4,137 views, and 5 podcast episodes, serves as a repository for project-related recordings, including Festivals and Webstivals. All social media KPIs are monitored and closely tracked monthly through a social media planner.

Figure 9. Climateurope2 YouTube channel

What worked well and areas for improvement

One of the most effective approaches has been leveraging the Network to extend the reach and visibility of activities and events. Encouraging participants and partners to share content through their own channels helps amplify dissemination efforts and engage audiences beyond the immediate project followers.

Experience from recent activities also shows that live posting and real-time social media engagement are generally more effective during in-person events, where participants tend to interact more actively and share content spontaneously. By contrast, online events usually generate lower levels of immediate interaction and visibility. To make an example, engagement tends to be lower during Webstivals than during in-person Festival events, likely because face-to-face participation fosters stronger networking opportunities, discussion, and audience involvement.

4 Events for engagement

4.1 Climateurope2 webinars

A minimum of six webinars delivered by representatives of the climate services community are planned over the lifetime of the Climateurope2 project in order to assess stakeholder responses to project outcomes and identify new opportunities. To date, eight webinars have been delivered⁴. Five of them have already been reported in previous deliverables, whereas three more have been organised since the submission of the previous deliverable. These are part of the **Stakeholders' Perspectives webinar series**, which aims to better understand stakeholder needs related to climate services and their standardisation. Each session focuses on a specific stakeholder group, gathering insights into their

⁴ See the Annex for the complete list

experiences, expectations, and requirements for integrating climate-related information into day-to-day activities. These targeted webinars address relevant topics and narratives for different audiences, with the overall objective of strengthening community engagement and supporting its continued growth.

The first new webinar, **Urban Planning through the Lens of Equity**, took place on 5 June 2025 and explored needs for climate information and services in the field of urban planning, with the aim of identifying challenges and recommendations for urban policymaking. To provide both local and European administrative perspectives, speakers included Minerva Campos from Àrea Metropolitana de Barcelona and Julia Rawlins from ICLEI. The session was moderated by Marina Baldissera from the Barcelona Supercomputing Center and University College London. A total of **81 participants** attended the webinar.

The second webinar, dedicated to the **Climateurope2 Platform**, took place on 27 November 2025 and marked its official launch. During the session, participants were introduced to the platform and its functionalities through a live walkthrough led by project partners involved in its development. Speakers included Tjerk Krijger, Project Engineer at MARIS B.V.; Kelsey Bailey, Product Designer at the Barcelona Supercomputing Center; and Arno Scharl, Managing Partner of webLyzard technology. A total of **71 participants** attended the webinar.

The last Stakeholders' Perspectives webinar was held on 18 May 2026 and focused on the **education sector**. The session explored how the needs of educational institutions, identified through interactions with students, can inform the standardisation of climate services. Speakers included Simon Wild, Project Manager at Frankfurt School of Finance & Management, and Raül Marcos, Professor at Universitat de Barcelona and Researcher at the Barcelona Supercomputing Center. The webinar was moderated by Judith Klostermann from Wageningen University & Research. A total of **42 participants** attended the webinar.

All webinars were recorded and uploaded to the project website in compliance with General Data Protection Regulation requirements.

What worked well

These webinars successfully fulfilled their objective of showcasing perspectives from different sectors and were very well received by participants. One of their main added values was encouraging speakers to actively reflect on how the standardisation of climate services could benefit their sector and to address this in their presentations. In several cases, this was likely a reflection exercise that speakers would not have undertaken otherwise, making the webinars a valuable space for generating new perspectives and discussions.

Webinars continued to show high participation and strong response rates in post-event surveys.

Table 1. Response rates in post-webinar surveys

Webinar	Date	Rate average
Urban planning through the lens of equity	5 June 2025	8.7/10

The platform that connects the climate services community	27 November 2025	8.6/10
Perspectives from the education sector	18 May 2026	8.9/10

Engagement was notably higher when interactive elements, such as Mentimeter activities, were included. In addition, sessions featuring two contrasting perspectives proved more dynamic and helped sustain audience attention and involvement.

Areas for improvement

Audience drop-off typically increases after the first hour of the webinar. However, we still consider 90 minutes an appropriate length, as it allows sufficient time for presentations and a dedicated discussion in the last half hour. That said, strategies to better sustain audience engagement during this final discussion segment could be further improved to help maintain participation until the end.

At times, we struggled to reach some target audiences because we lacked direct communication channels with certain sectors. This could have been improved by developing, from the beginning of the project, a more targeted audience engagement strategy focused on better understanding key stakeholder groups and the communication channels most relevant to them.

4.2 Webstivals and Festivals

Webstivals and Festivals are among the key events organised by CE2 to engage a diverse range of stakeholders. To date, five online Webstivals and two in-person Festivals have been held on a semi-annual basis (M6, M12, M24, M31, M45). A final Webstival is planned for later this year, before the end of the project. Table 2, below, provides an overview of the Webstivals and Festivals organised to date.

Table 2. Climateurope2 Webstivals and Festivals organised to date

Date	Title	Type of event	Link
22-24 March 2023	Science and society dialogues on climate services and innovation	Webstival (Online)	Link
19-20 September 2023	Businesses and communities: climate services for a resilient Europe	Webstival (Online)	Link
11-13 March 2024	Uniting science, services, and standards for a climate-resilient future	In-person Festival (Venice, Italy)	Link
19-20 September 2024	Excellence in climate services for transformational change	Webstival (Online)	Link

11-12 March 2025	Climate services for cities – shaping climate adaptation and mitigation actions	Webstival (Online)	Link
29 September-1 October 2025	Empowering society through climate services	In-person Festival (Belgrade, Serbia)	Link
15-17 April 2026	Climate Services Standardisation: Emerging Developments in AI and Co-Production	Webstival (Online)	Link

The organisation of Webstivals and Festivals is led by CMCC, with contributions from all work packages and external participants, including relevant European projects and private-sector stakeholders.

The first four Webstivals and the Festival held in Venice were described in previous deliverables (see [D6.2](#) and [D6.3](#)). In the past year, the second Festival (29 September – 1 October 2025) and the fifth Webstival (15–17 April 2026) have taken place.

Under the title "[Empowering society through climate services](#)", the **second** in-person Climateurope2 **Festival** was held in Belgrade, Serbia, from 29 September to 1 October 2025. The event was designed to blend interactive activities and insightful presentations. It combined plenary sessions, breakout sessions, interactive sessions, World Café discussions, a Marketplace, and art+science formats.

The first day of the Festival included a high-level side event led by WP5 and organised by WP6. The high-level event was organised with policymakers from different governance levels across the Southeastern Europe region, positioned within the opening of the Festival and linked to the broader discussion on climate services, regional dialogue, and enabling action.

Across the three days, the programme combined interactive and participatory formats focused on climate service development, regional exchange in southeastern Europe, agriculture and public health, user experience and practical application, future adaptation, and final collective reflection on the Festival discussions.

The programme also included a dedicated regional dimension, particularly through sessions focused on southeastern Europe. This supported the continued visibility of the region within the Climateurope2 community and strengthened links between regional actors and the wider European climate services network. The sessions covered themes such as co-production, agriculture, health, climate services market development, local tools and solutions, and resilient urban development. The agenda alternated plenary sessions and interactive parallel ones, delving into more specific topics with a smaller audience. The World Café format was organised in the context of the interactive sessions. It was organised in two rounds and included 16 contributions in total.

Figure 10. Visual agenda of the second CE2 Festival. [A more detailed version](#), including descriptions of each session, speakers, and venue information, was provided to participants

Monday, 29th Sep		Tuesday, 30th Sep		Wednesday, 1st Oct	
13:00	Registration & welcome coffee	9:30	A Dialogue on the Meaning and Purpose Climate Service	9:30	All You Need Is Health: Climate Services for Health
14:00		11:00		11:00	
14:00	Expanding the Reach of Climate Services: Connecting Regions, Enabling Action	11:30	Interactive Session	11:30	Interactive Session
15:00		13:00	How to Build a Climate Service	13:00	The Future of Climate Services
			Marketplace		
15:00	Climate Dialogues in Southeast Europe: Innovation, Impact, Inclusion	14:15	Seeds of Change: Climate Services for Agriculture	14:30	Mission Adaptation in the Region - Dialogue
16:30		15:45		16:00	
17:00	Exhibition presentation	16:15	Interactive Session & World Café	16:30	Finale & Feedback: Honouring Interactions
17:30	Climate Services through Art & Science	17:45	Climate Service - The Experience	18:00	
17:30					
18:30	Marketplace				
18:30					
18:30	Cocktail - Food & music				
19:30					

The Marketplace was an important engagement component of the Festival, running in parallel throughout the whole event. It included 7 exhibitor tables, 9 posters, 1 stand dedicated to the Climateurope2 project managed by WP6, and 4 roll-ups. These contributions involved research institutions, meteorological services, international organisations, development actors, NGOs, and EU-funded projects.

The Art+science projects [M1L3NA](#), [Breathing](#), [the Climate Capsule](#), and Mind the Time/Weather ([Pogledaj \(na\) vreme](#)) were another important engagement line during the Festival. Presentations of these projects were integrated into the Festival programme alongside plenary, breakout, and networking activities.

A series of initiatives were implemented to engage and involve participants from different sectors and levels of expertise. For example, a special edition of the magazine Elementi was published for the occasion of the Festival, exploring the role of science, technology, and creativity in building a climate-resilient future. In addition, a scribe illustrated in real time the main results and discussions from the various plenary sessions of the Festival. Both the [magazine](#) and the [illustrations](#) are available on the Climateurope2 website as supplementary Festival materials. Two of the illustrations are reproduced below (Figure 11):

Figure 11. Two illustrations capturing the main topics tackled during the first and third sessions of the Festival.

Oral presentations were provided by a mix of invited experts and selected participants. In total, there were 74 speakers, including panellists, keynote speakers, and moderators of parallel sessions. Gender balance was considered, resulting in 42 female speakers (57%) and 32 male speakers (42%). Several European projects were featured across keynote sessions, parallel sessions and the marketplace,

alongside other national and local initiatives, as listed in the table below. In addition, all work packages organised their own dedicated activities during the parallel sessions.

Table 3. Projects and initiatives showcased during the Climateurope2 Festival in Belgrade

Project Type	Projects / Initiatives
Horizon Europe / Horizon 2020 Projects	CLIMAAX , Adaptation AGORA , ASPECT , CLIMOS , PLANET4HEALTH , ARCADIA , SDGs-EYES , TRIGGER , Pathway2Resilience , Impetus4Change , REACHOUT , COALESCE , IDAlert , ClimaPannonia , FOCUS AFRICA
Interreg / Territorial Cooperation	GRECALE , NATURED , ARIANNA , URBANFLOODS , BEALERT , Clim4Cast , X-RISK-CC
LIFE Programme	LIFE4ADAPT
Local / National Initiatives or Platforms	UrbanFoS , Agrometeo.mk , PIM-PAM
Private Organisations / Associations	Hylosense (formerly known as EarthCare.ai), The Association for Farmers Rights Defense (AFRD)
International (non-EU) Initiatives	World Bank , DMCSEE

163 participants attended the Festival over three days, including around 20 online participants. According to the Festival records, this included 140 registered participants (of which 46 were Climateurope2 partners), and 23 participants not previously registered. The gender breakdown was 98 female participants (61%), 62 male participants (38%), and 1 participant who preferred not to say. The Festival also showed broad sectoral and geographic participation. “Research and Academia” remained the largest group (around 50%), followed by other stakeholders (21%), public administration (13%), and business (12%), while NGOs, associations, and media had smaller shares. The strongest national participation came from Serbia (approximately 61%), alongside participants from a wider set of European countries.

Figure 12. Group photo of the participants of the Climateurope2 Festival in Belgrade

The **5th Webstival**, titled "[Climate Services Standardisation: Emerging Developments in AI and Co-Production](#)", was held online from 15 to 17 April 2026. To develop the agenda for this edition, the Programme Committee decided to involve the community more actively by launching a survey through the social media channel LinkedIn and the CE2 newsletter, to collect suggestions and preferences on topics and formats. On LinkedIn, four poll posts were published over a ten-day period, each running for two weeks. Besides the overarching topic of Standardisation of Climate Services, co-production, artificial intelligence (AI) and specific sectorial foci such as agriculture, water and insurance & finance were identified as the key topics for this Webstival.

The Webstival agenda was designed over three half days, with two sessions scheduled per morning. Each day was structured in one plenary session and one more interactive or breakout session, addressing one overarching theme per day. The first day was dedicated to the co-production and the standardisation process, the second to AI in climate services, and the third to sectoral perspectives with special emphasis on the previous topics.

Figure 13. Visual agenda of the Fifth CE2 Webstival

The speakers were in part members of the Climateurope2 project, and in part invited experts from relevant projects and organisations. In total, there were 36 speakers including keynote speakers, panellists and moderators, of which 13 were female (36%) and 23 male (64%). Several initiatives were showcased, such as the Horizon Project [PCP WISE](#) and initiatives such as [DestinationEarth](#), [ClimateGPT](#), [C3S](#).

A total of 157 participants attended over the three days, including 70 representatives from partner institutions involved in the project. As in previous editions, the sectoral composition of participants is primarily concentrated in Research & Academia, which accounts for approximately 47% of attendees, confirming the strong scientific orientation of the initiative. The business sector represents about 23% of participants, indicating a solid and growing involvement of private stakeholders. Public Administration accounts for roughly 15%, reflecting a meaningful contribution from institutional actors engaged in policy and implementation. The “Other” category makes up around 12%, while Media (about 2%) and NGOs & Associations (around 1%) remain marginal. In terms of geographical distribution, although most participants came from Central and Western Europe, with 18% from Germany, 13% from the United Kingdom, and another 13% from Spain, there was also a relevant representation from Southeastern Europe. In particular, Serbia accounted for 6% of participants, complemented by smaller shares from Albania, Bulgaria, Greece, Croatia, and Slovenia.

The **final Webstival** will be held before the end of 2026, before the project’s Final General Assembly. The Programme Committee decided to slightly postpone the webstival (compared to previous editions) so that it will represent a moment of closure and reflection. As the last edition of the series, it will place particular emphasis on showcasing the project’s main achievements, lessons learned, and success stories, while also creating space to reflect on future perspectives. In this sense, it will play a crucial role in consolidating results and laying the foundations for a strong and lasting legacy beyond the project’s lifetime.

Participants feedback has been gathered in two ways in each event: through a real-time Mentimeter survey during the closing session of each event; and through a post-event survey sent to every participant. Below is an overview of what went well and what could be improved.

What worked well in the Festival

The evaluation results indicate that the Belgrade Climateurope2 Festival was very positively received by participants, both in terms of content and overall experience. The post-event survey and Mentimeter feedback show that the Festival successfully created a welcoming, engaging and community-oriented environment, with networking emerging as one of the strongest values of the event. In the Mentimeter feedback, networking was the main motivation for participation, selected by 62% of respondents, followed by learning about climate services and regional climate science. Participants particularly appreciated the friendly atmosphere, the opportunity to meet and reconnect with colleagues, the focus on South-Eastern and Eastern Europe, and the diversity of formats, including panel discussions, world café sessions, marketplace activities, art and music.

The detailed evaluation further confirmed the strong quality of the Festival. Among 30 respondents, 90% agreed or strongly agreed that the knowledge gained was valuable, 87% found the workshops engaging and useful, 93% considered the panel sessions interesting, and 87% felt they had enough time to network. The overall rating of the quality was very high, with an average score of 4.58 out of 5. At the same time, the feedback suggested some improvements for future editions: participants would welcome more technical or topic-specific sessions, stronger structured networking, more hands-on and marketplace-style activities, and a stronger involvement of actual climate service users throughout the programme. The comments also suggest that future events should consider flexible planning for interactive sessions depending on attendance, earlier programme communication, and further inclusion of diverse stakeholder voices, including young people, PhD researchers, business/practice representatives and vulnerable groups.

What worked well in Webstivals

Feedback gathered through real-time Mentimeter polling and feedback surveys across multiple Webstivals highlights the strong value of interactive, discussion-led formats in engaging the climate services community. Participants consistently emphasised the diversity of perspectives, the openness of discussions, and the balance between expert input and audience interaction as key strengths. Sessions focusing on AI, standardisation, co-production and storytelling were frequently cited as particularly valuable, with respondents describing the Webstivals as “engaging”, “informative”, “interactive” and “inspiring”. The use of shorter sessions spread over multiple half-days was also positively received, as it supported sustained engagement while remaining compatible with participants’ professional commitments. Together, this indicates that Webstivals are most effective when designed as participatory forums that prioritise dialogue, interdisciplinary exchange and practical reflection over one-way knowledge transfer.

Areas for improvement and future direction of Webstivals

At the same time, feedback points to clear opportunities for refinement. Participants expressed a strong desire for greater involvement of end users, policymakers and private-sector actors, with more real-world case studies, user stories and demonstrations of climate services in practice. While interactive tools such as Mentimeter were widely appreciated, some respondents highlighted the need for balance, suggesting fewer but more targeted uses to allow deeper discussion. Requests for greater thematic diversity (e.g. health, agriculture, tourism, infrastructure), as well as stronger representation of underrepresented groups and regions, reinforce the importance of inclusivity in future event design. Collectively, these insights underline the need to continue evolving the Webstival format towards more user-led, application-focused and socially grounded engagement, while retaining the interactive and

community-oriented elements that participants clearly value. Figure 14 summarises the feedback gathered over the Webstivals into 4 themes: format and engagement, content and focus, community and inclusion, and future improvements.

Figure 14. Thematic synthesis of qualitative feedback collected through Mentimeter polls and surveys during Climateurope2 Webstivals, highlighting strengths of the event format and priorities for future iterations

4.3 Roadshow

A major WP6 engagement activity during the project was the Travelling Climate Action – Roadshow, coordinated by the Centre for the Promotion of Science (CPN). The Roadshow was developed as a regional outreach and engagement format to promote climate services through a combination of stakeholder dialogue, public-facing activities, and art+science formats. Its main strategic value within WP6 lay in its ability to expand the Climateurope2 community in southeastern Europe, a region that has remained comparatively underrepresented in the European climate services landscape. The Roadshow therefore served as a dissemination activity and as a mechanism for network expansion, local stakeholder engagement, and increased visibility of climate services in new regional contexts.

The [first cycle of the Roadshow](#) covered five locations across southeastern Europe: Rijeka (Croatia) and Tirana (Albania) on 19–25 June 2024, Kotor (Montenegro) on 11–14 August 2024, Sarajevo (Bosnia and Herzegovina) on 3–5 October 2024, and Skopje (North Macedonia) on 5 December 2024. Across these five locations, the Roadshow reached more than 200 participants and contributed to the growth of the Climateurope2 Network with 69 new community members, of whom 49 were from southeastern Europe.

An important feature of the Roadshow was its collaborative development with local partners, which supported contextual relevance and stronger local anchoring in each location. The Roadshow began in Rijeka, Croatia, in cooperation with the Faculty of Physics at the University of Rijeka. In Tirana, Albania,

the Roadshow was developed in collaboration with the Albanian Gaming Community, within the broader cooperation with the Serbian Game Association (SGA) through the Playing Narratives regional programme due to lack of strong partners in the field on the local. In Kotor, Montenegro, activities were developed with the Institute of Marine Biology at the University of Montenegro, as combined with the Kotor Art Festival, in order to get wider reach to the general audience. In Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina, the Roadshow was organised in collaboration with the Verlab Institute, while in Skopje, North Macedonia, it was held in partnership with the Faculty of Computer Science and Engineering at the University of “St. Cyril and Methodius”.

This local-partner model was a relevant element of the Roadshow design, as it helped connect the Climateurope2 consortium with place-based institutions and stakeholder communities in each city. Moreover, at every roadshow location, local MetService was invited to participate at the local stakeholder event, and to contribute to the agenda with recommendations of local speakers who represent best practice examples of local use of climate services, as well as by recommendations of stakeholders-potential users of climate services, that should be invited to the audience.

In terms of format, the Roadshow combined stakeholder-oriented events with a broader public engagement dimension. The stakeholder component usually took the form of a panel discussion focused on the practical use of climate information, the role of climate services in decision-making, and locally relevant climate challenges. The topics discussed varied by location and reflected local contexts, while still remaining connected to the broader Climateurope2 objective of building understanding and use of climate services. Participants included representatives from research and academia, public institutions, the private sector, civil society, and other local actors interested in climate change and climate-related decision-making. This made the Roadshow particularly useful as an entry point for dialogue across different parts of the climate services value chain that are not always engaged through more conventional conference-based formats.

Alongside the stakeholder discussions, the Roadshow incorporated a strong art+science engagement line, which distinguished it from more standard project events. The main recurring format was the Climate Capsule, a mobile and modular installation designed to offer an immersive and layered perspective on climate change through scientific facts, multimedia content, and artistic interventions.

The Roadshow also presented “M1L3NA”, the winning project of the first Climateurope2 art+science open call, by Serbian art collective “Three penny”, which offered each visitor a personalised future-oriented experience in the context of climate change. These installations functioned as more accessible entry points into the topic of climate services and helped broaden participation beyond the narrower circle of technical or policy stakeholders. The first five Roadshow locations were also documented in a [promotional video](#) produced by CPN and published in November 2024, which added a further communication layer to the activity and supported its visibility beyond the events themselves.

A new cycle of the Roadshow - Travelling Climate Action was launched in March 2026, with events in Romania, Hungary, Greece, Slovenia, and Bulgaria from March until June 2026. Building on the first cycle, these activities were prepared in cooperation with regional and local partners and combined stakeholder engagement formats with Climate Capsule installations and followed by the winners of the second open art+science call - [BREATHING](#) by French artist Arnaud Laffond. The first event of this cycle was held in Cluj-Napoca, Romania, on 24–25 March 2026, in cooperation with Babeş-Bolyai University, Faculty of Geography, and as a joint activity with the [SCEWERO](#) project, which included a dedicated session with local stakeholders on CE2 platform. Over the two days, the Climate Capsule engaged over 300 pupils, students, and teachers, while the accompanying workshop, Science

Communication as a Bridge Between Climate Research and Climate Services, brought together 47 participants.

The Roadshow in **Keszthely, Hungary**, was on 15–16 April 2026, organized in partnership with the [DIRECTED](#) project and in connection with the annual Helikon arts and youth Festival in the Zala region. Although the planned panel discussion had to be cancelled at short notice due to political circumstances, the Climate Capsule installation was nevertheless implemented and attracted more than 130 visitors. The Roadshow in **Athens, Greece**, was held 21–24 April 2026, in cooperation with partners at the Institute of Environmental Research of the National Observatory of Athens and with the Municipality of Athens, attended by 47 people at the Municipality of Athens. The fourth event was organized in **Burgas, Bulgaria**, on 28–30 May 2026, in cooperation with the Municipality of Burgas. The fifth and final event was organised in **Trbovlje, Slovenia**, on 5–6 June 2026, in cooperation with Delavski dom Trbovlje. These events were designed to combine local panel discussions with Climate Capsule and the BREATHING installations in accessible public locations, continuing the Roadshow model developed in the first cycle.

What worked well

Several aspects of the Roadshow appear to have worked particularly well. First, the activity succeeded in extending the geographical reach of Climateurope2 into southeastern Europe and in supporting tangible community growth. The increase in membership following the first Roadshow cycle suggests that the format was effective in converting event participation into more durable forms of network connection. Second, the combination of local partnership-building and regional coordination provided a strong operational model. By relying on local partners in each city, the Roadshow was able to remain locally grounded while still maintaining a recognisable Climateurope2 identity across locations. Third, the combination of stakeholder panels with art+science installations proved to be a distinctive strength. This hybrid format expanded the range of participants that could be meaningfully engaged and created multiple points of access to the topic, from expert discussion to experiential public interaction. Fourth, the Roadshow helped position climate services not only as a scientific & technical domain, but also as a socially relevant and publicly communicable field, which is consistent with the broader aims of WP6 regarding inclusion, visibility, and community-building.

A further strength was the adaptability of the format across locations. While the core structure remained recognisable, the thematic focus of panels could be adjusted to reflect local issues and institutional settings. This helped avoid a one-size-fits-all model and made it possible to respond to the interests of different stakeholder communities, including those linked to marine environments, air quality, agriculture, hydrology, meteorology, and local climate impacts. In practical terms, this adaptability increased the relevance of the events and supported a more credible connection between European-level project objectives and local or regional concerns.

Areas for improvement and future direction

At the same time, the Roadshow experience points to areas where future cycles could strengthen the depth and continuity of engagement after the event itself. While the Roadshow was effective as a first contact and awareness-raising format, the available material provides much stronger evidence on attendance and new memberships than on longer-term follow-up, such as continued participation of attendees in the Climateurope2 Network or subsequent uptake of climate services-related collaboration. Future Roadshow cycles would benefit from a more explicit post-event follow-up model, including structured mechanisms for keeping newly engaged participants active within the network.

4.4 Other initiatives organised in the context of Climateurope2

In addition, the Roadshow model was extended through a further outreach activity in Svilajnac, Serbia, on 26 September 2025, organised within the European Researchers' Night programme, where the Climate Capsule and related interactive content were used to engage citizens, students, and teachers around climate services and climate change. The Climateurope2 art+science engagement line was also further presented within the jubilee edition of the art+science Festival in Belgrade, held from 7 to 26 October 2025 at Silosi, where selected Climateurope2-related works and formats, including Breathing, M1L3NΛ, and Mind the Time/Weather (Pogledaj (na) vreme), were shown in a wider programme dedicated to the intersection of science, art, technology and society.

Further public engagement activities helped extend the reach of Climateurope2 beyond the Festival itself. At the [65th International Fair of Technics and Technical Achievements](#), held from 16 to 19 May 2023 at the Belgrade Fair, CPN presented the Climate Capsule within the national exhibition *Play for Humanity! Science for All*. The Climate Capsule was also presented at the [17th Science Festival](#) in Belgrade, held from 12 to 14 December 2024, together with an educational and interactive programme addressing climate change.

In 2025, the exhibition [Climate Action through Poetry and Photography](#) was presented at the Belgrade Fortress from 6 to 26 October, showcasing works selected through a regional open call organised within Climateurope2 roadshow initiative and using poetry and photography to stimulate public dialogue on climate change and its effects on our surroundings. The exhibition was followed by a publication. The Climateurope2 project also supported the new edition of [Hell of a Story](#), the first climate journalism school in Serbia, aimed at young journalists and content creators interested in climate change topics. The school connects journalistic skills, climate science and contemporary storytelling formats, and is organised through three in-person workshops in April, May and June 2026, with additional online meetings and mentoring support throughout the programme.

What worked well

The activities showed that large-scale public events connected to science, culture and public engagement are particularly effective environments for introducing complex climate-related topics to wider audiences. Named formats created accessible entry points for engaging with climate change, climate services and climate action. By combining scientific information with artistic, interactive and participatory formats, these initiatives helped audiences approach demanding topics in a more open, intuitive and emotionally resonant way.

It also worked well to embed Climateurope2 content within already established public events, as this made it possible to reach broader and more diverse audiences, including people who might not normally attend specialised climate-focused activities. These formats lowered the barrier to participation and created space for curiosity, dialogue and reflection.

Areas for improvement and future direction

Future activities should continue using public science and culture events as platforms for climate communication, while further strengthening the link between engagement formats and the concept of climate services. More attention could be given to helping audiences understand not only the broader relevance of climate change, but also how climate services can be used in everyday decision-making, education, local planning and community action.

A future direction could also be to develop more structured follow-up formats after large public events, such as workshops, school activities, guided discussions or digital resources. This would help transform initial audience interest into deeper understanding, continued engagement and practical use of Climateurope2 materials beyond the event itself.

4.5 Sectoral workshops

A series of successful invitation-only workshops have been organised by WP8. The aims of these events were to inform key sectoral stakeholders about the standardisation processes, to collect sector-specific insights and recommendations, to align CE2 recommendations with sector-specific needs and to foster exchange and stronger networks. The workshops had a consistent format, applying a structured approach of presentations by prominent expert speakers followed by a series of interactive breakout 'sprints'. Expert facilitators guided small breakout groups through structured discussions on climate services and standardisation in the context of the sector, using pre-designed prompts. This method generated systematic, comparable data in a participatory and engaging format.

The first was a [workshop focused on private climate services providers](#). It brought together 21 participants from 18 companies (small, medium and large) from across Europe on 28-29 April 2025 in Barcelona. Several keynote speeches were given, including by WMO, DG Clima, and the CE2 PI at BSC.

The second [workshop focused on the health sector](#) and took place over 9-10 September 2025. Participants included climate service providers, public health and epidemiology experts, humanitarian and early-warning specialists, global funders, researchers, and policymakers from leading international organisations. Presentations were given by WMO, the Red Cross Climate Centre and ECMWF. The hybrid format allowed global participation using online streaming and breakout groups using Miro. This made the workshop more accessible to smaller, resource-constrained, or geographically distant organisations.

The next event focused on [climate analytics in the re/insurance, finance and banking sector](#). 35 participants including providers, asset managers, insurers, and regulators attended in London on 21-22 October 2025. Speakers included ECMWF, the European Investment Bank, EIOPA and CEN.

Most recently, the fourth online [workshop with National Meteorological and Hydrological Services](#) (NMHSs) was convened on 15 January 2026, with keynotes from WMO and C3S. 36 attendees from 25 organisations participated in the sprints to represent the public climate service provider viewpoint. Participation was principally by European NMHSs, from countries across all regions of Europe. There was additionally representation from NMHSs from other regions globally, EUMETSAT, WMO and ECMWF.

Following the events, the data from the sprints were analysed, focused on identifying recurring themes, key differences in perspectives, and emerging patterns relevant to the research objectives. [Joint statements](#) have synthesised the findings to set out sectoral positions on climate services standardisation as established through the workshops. Where appropriate, these public statements were endorsed by attendees, giving the publications further legitimacy and credibility. These publications are in draft for the two most recent events (finance and NMHSs) at the time of writing this deliverable.

The 5th workshop in this series is planned for 22-23 October 2026 and will focus on the renewable energy sector. Participants will represent a range of actors across the European landscape, including project developers, owners and operators; financial institutions; providers of climate services, certification and consulting; energy traders and investors, and model developers.

The events have been invaluable in understanding the landscape of climate services, and perspectives, preferences and constraints relevant to standardisation for each sector. The outcome of these events will also provide valuable input for the development of the first standards for climate services which is currently ongoing by CEN-CENELEC. A further key outcome of the events will be continued dialogue between the participants.

What worked well

The opportunity for the events to convene sector-specific climate services communities was received very positively by attendees. Thus, the events not only met the goal to inform about CE2 and the standardisation process but also supported community-building and facilitation of cooperation and communication. As the events brought together a broad range of groups including providers, users, regulators for focused, productive discussions, the mix of attendees has been a clear benefit. The format of the “sprints” was very effective for discussing and sharing the different perspectives of the participants. The format worked well both in-person and online, using paper templates and Miro boards respectively. Similarly to the roadshows, the core structure and approach of all events remained comparable, whilst detailed questions and information were adjusted specifically for each sector. This allows comparability and replicability between events and ensures the good practices are maintained, whilst ensuring it is tailored to each stakeholder group in order to effectively draw out sector-specific insights.

Areas for improvement and future direction

There were technical and logistical challenges to delivering an interactive event in hybrid format, as was the case for the health workshop. This was principally in the plenary elements in which the groups were brought together for a whole-group discussion. The outcome was successful, however, if further workshops of this type were planned, it would be carefully considered whether the added benefit of hybrid participation outweighs the effort needed to deliver an event in this format effectively. The final sectoral workshop will take place as an in-person only event.

4.6 Sessions and side events in other conferences

Several important European conferences which focus on topics such as climate change and climate adaptation provide valuable opportunities for Climateurope2 to engage new audiences and disseminate results. Several contributions from Climateurope2 to major conferences have been reported in previous deliverables. Some of the major scientific conferences that took place since the last deliverable are listed in Table 4.

Table 4. European conferences of interest for the project

Acronym	Full title	Schedule	Audience
ECCA	European Conference on Climate Change Adaptation	16-18 June 2025 (Rimini, Italy) (bi-annual meeting)	Scientific and non-scientific climate adaptation community
EGU	European Geosciences Union	27 April–2 May 2025 3–8 May 2026 (Vienna, Austria) (annual meetings)	Scientists in the Earth, planetary and space sciences
EMS	European Meteorological Society	06–11 September 2026 (Utrecht, Netherlands) (annual meetings)	Scientists, practitioners, policy makers, industry

Several members of the CE2 consortium attended these meetings and organized or contributed to sessions of these meetings, for instance:

- Representatives from LGI presented the work developed in WP4 during a roundtable on Climate Services at ECCA in Rimini (Italy).
- At a panel session at the 7th Nordic Annual Environmental and Resource Economics Meeting ([NAERE](#)) in Kongens Lyngby (Denmark), on 25–26 June 2025, DTU presented the results from stakeholder consultations conducted in WP3 on the value of Climate Services.
- Partners in Barcelona Supercomputing Center presented a poster on “Co-production of fit-for-purpose climate services: An example from the health sector,” at the [Congress on Social Communication of Science](#) in Palma de Mallorca (Spain), 2–6 October 2025.
- At EGU2026 partners from SMHI organised a [townhall](#) to present some of the project's latest achievements, such as the set of recommendations on data and processes covering metadata and standards, traceability, verification, and uncertainty and climate risk assessment. At the same conference, partners from DTU also presented a paper consolidating the work done in WP3 on economic, social, and environmental values and benefits of climate services.
- WP3 will also present at the next EMS2026, during the session "[ES1.6](#) Values, Benefits, and Uptake of Climate Services: Co-Creation and Societal Impact".

Moreover, other initiatives were exploited to disseminate results developed in the project. For instance,

- During the European Researchers' Night, on the 29 September 2025 in Sweden, SMHI organised seminars and hands-on activity for students.
- In Serbia, for the European Researchers' Night on 26 September 2025, CPN organised activities for public engagement, including a display of the above-mentioned Climate Capsule.
- Climate-KIC presented the work developed in WP4 during panel discussions and presentations at [EU LAC Digital Alliance week](#) in Antigua (Guatemala), on 22–26 September 2025, focusing on cooperation between the LAC region and Europe on the use of EO data and climate services.
- At the [Copernicus General Assembly](#) in Budapest (June 2026), a side meeting titled “The Future of Climate Services” was organised. During the meeting, two interactive sessions were held in which key messages of the CE2 project for improving quality of services and standardization of climate services were discussed.

5 Involvement of the WPs in community engagement

Engaging with the climate services community is a collective effort that requires strong coordination within the Climateurope2 project. Engaged stakeholders should experience a coherent and consistent approach across all activities. With respect to the stakeholder engagement activities planned by each work package this requires an effective internal communication.

As Climateurope2 brings together 33 partners across 8 work packages, WP6 has established a cross-WP coordination strategy to support effective communication and collaboration throughout the project. This approach involves WP6 members regularly participating in meetings of the Management Board and cross WP1–WP5 meetings, in order to remain informed about ongoing activities and to share updates on their own initiatives. In this way, WP6 facilitates feedback and dialogue across WPs, helping to strengthen connections within the consortium and foster collaboration.

With respect to the organization of events such as the Webstivals and Festivals, one of the primary ways WP6 interacts with the other work packages are the Programme Committee meeting. The Programme Committee, led by WP6, includes representatives from each WP and meets every two weeks during the months preceding each event. This schedule ensures that contributions and perspectives from all WPs are integrated into the event programmes, while also strengthening communication flows between the

internal activities of the project and its wider external community engagement. In addition, selected WPs and project experts are actively involved in other engagement activities, including sectoral workshops and the stakeholder engagement webinar series.

This approach follows the WP6-developed community-building roadmap, which has been presented in previous deliverables and progressively refined (Figure 15). The roadmap includes both internal and external dimensions. Internally, it focuses on promoting coherent collaboration among the WPs to support active and coordinated community engagement. Externally, it aims to attract new community members while ensuring that existing members remain informed, involved, and engaged throughout the project.

Figure 15. Community-building roadmap developed by WP6

6 Recommendations for engagement events and activities in future initiatives

In this section, we review the main approaches that proved to be effective and successful, as well as the challenges that still persist in engaging the community, and we provide some recommendations for future initiatives interested in the continued development of the climate services community.

Throughout the four years of the project, the community expanded significantly, both geographically and in terms of participation, reaching not only to scientific and technical stakeholders but increasingly also the (private) business sector, public administrations, and NGOs. Precisely because of this diversity of users, it is important to continue keeping the community aligned and connected beyond the end of the project.

6.1 Recommendations on the channels for engagement

The communication and engagement channels developed throughout the project proved to be valuable tools for supporting the visibility, accessibility, and long-term sustainability of Climateurope2 activities

and products. In particular, the CE2 website and the Climateurope2 Platform are centralised access points where the community can find information on project activities, events, publications, guidelines, training materials, and stakeholder resources. Maintaining these resources in a structured and continuously updated way contributed significantly to strengthening community engagement and ensuring broad access to project results. Equally important is the navigability and usability of these tools, facilitating access to information and improving the overall user experience. Another important factor contributing to their effectiveness was the continuous promotion of these channels through communication activities, partner networks, newsletters, social media, and project events, which helped extend their visibility beyond the CE2 project community.

At the same time, throughout the implementation of the engagement strategy several areas for improvement emerged. One important challenge call for a more structured and continuous exchange with the wider climate services community, encouraging contributions from external stakeholders especially with regards to the use of the Platform, to contributions to the project blog, and to the broader exchange of information on external events and initiatives through the website and social media channels. In addition, expanding multilingual content would further improve accessibility and equitability.

One key recommendation for future initiatives is to continue promoting the digital communication channels in close integration with in-person engagement activities. As demonstrated particularly in the social media case, face-to-face events tend to generate stronger visibility and interaction, increasing online engagement and dissemination potential. In the case of the Platform, launching it during the second Festival and further promoting it through Webstivals and videos helped to increase the visibility of its potential applications to external audiences. For this reason, future projects should consider the use of communication channels and in-person events as complementary tools within a broader community-building strategy.

In the following section recommendations specifically related to engagement events and participatory formats are provided.

6.2 Recommendations on the events for engagement

In the previous sections, we outlined the main elements for community building that proved to be effective in engaging with a variety of stakeholders.

With respect to online events such as webinars, Webstivals and online workshops, positive elements welcomed by the participants were broad perspectives, openness of discussions, and the balance between expert input and audience interaction. Sessions that prioritised dialogue, interdisciplinary exchange, and practical reflection were generally perceived as more effective than formats based on one-way knowledge transfer.

At the same time, we observed that although interactive tools such as Mentimeter helped maintain audience engagement, participation levels still tended to decline during longer online meetings. Another observation is that online events tend to work better when tailored to a more targeted audience; however, reaching and effectively engaging the most relevant stakeholders for specific sectors or audience segments sometimes remains a significant challenge.

In-person events, such as Festivals, roadshows, and sectorial workshops, have proved to be very successful and particularly effective in engaging local and sectoral stakeholders. This allowed an active involvement, and often a first contact, with stakeholders from countries and sectors that are not always adequately represented in broader discussions on climate services. For instance, during the Roadshows in South-east Europe, local and trusted intermediaries were involved to organize the activities, showing

the interest and willingness to be engaged of many stakeholders. Moreover, through activities such as the art+science expositions, the events helped to understand climate services not only as a scientific or technical product, but also as a socially relevant and publicly communicable field. Another important strength was the consistency of the event formats: maintaining a stable structure for Festivals, workshops and roadshows allowing comparability and replicability between engagement activities and helped ensure that good practices were preserved and refined over time. However, one of the main challenges identified was the difficulty of keeping newly engaged participants actively involved within the network after the events.

Based on the experience gathered through both online and in-person engagement activities, future projects and initiatives could benefit from adopting a more targeted and locally tied approach. In the case of Webstivals, several formats were tested, but participation patterns proved to be inconsistent: while each event was generally able to attract new participants, these audiences did not automatically return for subsequent events. Even within a single webstival, participants often joined only for sessions directly relevant to their interests before disconnecting from the remainder of the programme. By contrast, in-person Festivals demonstrated a stronger capacity to maintain engagement and foster meaningful interaction.

Moreover, integrating events of different scales can be highly effective. In fact, our observations show that organizing a roadshow before a festival is advisable, as individuals engaged during the roadshow are more likely to travel to the festival for deeper knowledge exchange and networking. For this reason, future initiatives may benefit from organising smaller, more targeted in-person events tailored to specific sectors or countries, rather than relying primarily on large-scale Webstivals, which remain valuable but may be more effective if held less frequently. Table 5, below, shows the pattern of registration and participation in Webstivals and Festivals.

Table 5. Evolution of participants in Festivals and Webstivals

Date	Title	Type of event	Number of registered people	Number of actual participants
22-24 Mar 2023	Science and society dialogues on climate services and innovation	Webstival (Online)	492	263
19-20 Sep 2023	Businesses and communities: climate services for a resilient Europe	Webstival (Online)	447	236
11-13 Mar 2024	Uniting science, services, and standards for a climate-resilient future	In-person Festival (Venice, Italy)	156	140
19-20 Sep 2024	Excellence in climate services for transformational change	Webstival (Online)	355	210

Date	Title	Type of event	Number of registered people	Number of actual participants
11-12 Mar 2025	Climate services for cities – shaping climate adaptation and mitigation actions	Webstival (Online)	517	283
29 Sep-1 Oct 2025	Empowering society through climate services	In-person Festival (Belgrade, Serbia)	247	163
15-17 Apr 2026	Climate Services Standardisation: Emerging Developments in AI and Co-Production	Webstival (Online)	301	157

A key recommendation for in-person events is also to identify and collaborate closely with local partners that understand both climate services and the needs of local stakeholders and can help deliver information that is genuinely relevant for specific stakeholder groups. For achieving equitable climate services, methods need to be used that are sensitive to people with different capacities, needs and world views. Local and regional contexts need to be taken into account and visiting participants in their own region, especially underrepresented regions, is therefore helpful. At the same time, while being open to different world views and using the local context language is important, this should be balanced with the use of scientific definitions and standards to provide quality and create trust.

In addition, giving stakeholders themselves a more active role within events, for example through local projects or contributions from the private sector during Webstivals, has proved to strengthen participation and ownership.

Finally, integrating artistic and scientific approaches can play an important role in bringing climate services closer to the general public by introducing an emotional, cultural, and social dimension to climate change discussion. This approach can increase both the attractiveness and the perceived relevance of climate services, supporting their transition from a predominantly academic topic into mainstream public discourse. These approaches can also facilitate the dissemination of scientific knowledge even in contexts where scientists are not directly present, while still maintaining the communication of objective, evidence-based, and accessible information. Artists proved to be very interested in climate science and in visualizing what they had learned. Creating a feedback loop back from the artists to the scientists would be interesting to pursue this connection further and see what art has to teach to scientists.

Annex

Table 6. Stakeholder's Perspective webinars

Date	Title	link
21 June 2024	Stakeholders' perspectives webinar - Private sector	link
5 November 2024	Stakeholders' perspectives webinar - Communication and journalism sector	link
5 June 2025	Stakeholders' perspectives on urban planning through the lens of equity	link
27 November 2025	The platform that connects the climate services community	link
18 May 2026	Stakeholders' perspectives webinar - Education sector	link

Table 7. Other webinars

Date	Title	link
3 November 2022	UK climate services standards and value	link
25 May 2023	Art and science towards climate action	link
30 November 2023	Uncertainty in communication on climate services	link

Table 8. Evolution of the web/Festival format

Date	Title	Type of event	Number of days	Number of sessions	Number of subsessions	Total of hours (including breaks)
22-24 March 2023	Science and society dialogues on climate services and innovation	Online	3	6	12	18
19-20 September 2023	Businesses and communities: climate services for a resilient Europe	Online	2	7	11	13.5
11-13 March 2024	Uniting science, services, and standards for a climate-resilient future	In person (Venice, Italy)	3	10	27	40.5
19-20 September 2024	Excellence in climate services for transformational change	Online	2	5	11	11.25

Date	Title	Type of event	Number of days	Number of sessions	Number of subsessions	Total of hours (including breaks)
11-12 March 2025	Climate services for cities – shaping climate adaptation and mitigation actions	Online	2	6	6	11.5
29 September-1 October 2025	Empowering society through climate services	In person (Belgrade, Serbia)	3	10	22	23.5
15-17 April 2026	Climate Services Standardisation: Emerging Developments in AI and Co-Production	Online	3	6	11	10.5

Table 9. Speakers throughout the Web/Festivals

Date	Title	Number of speakers (including keynotes, moderators and panellists)	Number of female speakers	Number of countries represented by the speakers
22-24 March 2023	Science and society dialogues on climate services and innovation	60	30	14
19-20 September 2023	Businesses and communities: climate services for a resilient Europe	42	21	17
11-13 March 2024	Uniting science, services, and standards for a climate-resilient future	66	36	16
19-20 September 2024	Excellence in climate services for transformational change	36	15	13
11-12 March 2025	Climate services for cities – shaping climate adaptation and mitigation actions	40	20	20
29 September-1 October 2025	Empowering society through climate services	75	41	18
15-17 April 2026	Climate Services Standardisation: Emerging Developments in AI and Co-Production	36	13	11